

A conceptual exploration into the Indian concept of Mind and its role during the Covid-19 pandemic

Thejash M N

Research Scholar

*Department of Social Science and Humanities
Srinivas University*

ORCID – 0000-0002-2602-3222

Mangalore, India thejash_10@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Happiness has been the main goal for every human population. All activities carried out by humans are pointed towards gaining maximum happiness in life. We always assume that happiness is achieved by the accumulation of things, and hence we all search for happiness externally and the mind is external. As long as the mind wanders of objects, the mind is always uncontrolled, excited, agitated.

The mind is always dependent and food plays a major role in balancing our mind along with the body. It is difficult to control the mind when we starve for a couple of days without any prior experience. The body with its sense organs is also a substance of the mind. Our body is the external reality of the mind. All thoughts create a change to our body and this change when sent to the physical body causes nerve activities in the brain. Hence when the mind is hard, the body also becomes hard. And during deep sleep, there is no functioning of the mind.

The mind has a power of imagination that creates fear and during any pandemic situation, the fear intensifies and makes us the worst enemy. Studies have also discovered that COVID-19 has more correlation with fear and anxiety and also many have surrendered their life due to fear of Covid-19.

This paper,

- *This paper aims at exploring the concept of mind and its relationship with body and food*
- *The main objective is to understand the mechanism of the mind through a conceptual model and provide some recommendations to overcome fear and anxiety during the pandemic and achieve happiness*

We can overcome fear, and create a healthy life balance by purifying the mind through positive habits and practices.

Keywords: Mind, Indian Mind, pandemic, fear, anxiety, Psychological disorder, Conceptual model

INTRODUCTION

According to the west, the afferent nerves carry sensations from the spinal cord to the medulla from there they enter the superior frontal gyrus of the brain which is the place of self-awareness. The mind senses the vibration and directs the impulses through efferent nerves to the hands, legs, etc. Mind is the function of the brain and complete knowledge mind is still pitch dark.

Happiness has been a major goal for every human population. All activities carried out by humans are pointed towards gaining maximum happiness in life. But, we always assume that happiness is achieved by objects and hence humans search for happiness outward and the mind is externalized. The Mind is always restless, wandering, fluctuating, and always uncontrolled. To control this restless mind it's a challenge to mankind.

During any pandemic situation, most of our mind is always having fear and anxiety. Coping with fear and uncertainty is a big challenge and there are several unmet needs to address the psychological problems.

To get control of the mind, we need to understand what it is and how it works. This research paper helps us explore the meaning of the mind and how the mind works, and also explains to us how to control our mind through various methods and habits. Controlling the mind and adapting to coping strategies would help us achieve success in our life and also help us fight against any pandemic situation.

What is the mind? And different the types of mind

The mind is one of the most important and also most confused and confusing theories. The mind is an instrument that coordinates with senses or impulses, it is the instrument of thinking and perceiving information. It is unpredictable and vulnerable according to our desires and attachments. Hence, the Indian scriptures identify it as a source of suffering.

There are two types of mind

1. The Conscious mind (Individual mind)
2. Sub-conscious mind(Cosmic mind or universal mind)

On a general note, the mind and its existence are unknown, it cannot be measured, and there is no space for the mind. Mind is a subtle body that is formless and the mind can only be experienced.

1. Conscious mind: Conscious mind or Individual mind is also called an objective mind. This kind of mind always plays when the mind is in a waking state
2. Sub-Conscious mind: Sub-Conscious mind or Cosmic mind is also called the subjective mind and these consist of submerged experiences and memories

As Freud mentioned, only 10% of mental activities come into the conscious mind and 90% of activities take place in the Subconscious mind.

The Conscious Mind is the mind which we are always aware of every moment. We are aware of breathing, aware of the environment. The conscious mind talks to the external environment and to the self or soul through thinking, writing, speech, movement, etc. The fully developed conscious mind can focus and ability to distinguish between real and unreal.

The subconscious mind which is also called the subjective mind consists of all the data. We can get the awareness of all the data once we concentrate our mind on it. It acts as a memory recall. This is in charge of our recent memories. It is the power house of all the past involvements. It is from this memory our beliefs, habits, and behaviors are formed.

If we focus our thoughts on negative things, then our subconscious will deliver the feeling, emotions, and storage memories associated with negative thoughts. We would be caught in the web of negativity, fear, and anxiety. The Conscious mind is always connected to the sub-conscious mind and communicates through feelings, emotions, imaginations, and dreams.

Let us take an example:

When we are traveling on a train at night and get some strange noise in the night. If our thoughts think to all negative things that happen, then our subconscious will give feelings, emotions, and memories of past events that have been linked with these thoughts. On the other hand, if we constantly tell ourselves and direct our focus to more positive, peaceful thoughts then the feeling will disappear.

The Mind

Mind is a huge collection of data that we experience from birth to date. It's a huge bunch of habits learned. It is a collection of all desires, ideas, thoughts, and feelings arising from diverse experiences. These thoughts, desires, feelings, and ideas always change constantly. Old desires, ideas, and feelings are replaced by the new desires, ideas, and feelings from the storehouse called the mind. The habit makes the new thoughts, ideas, desires, and feelings are strongly held by the mind than the old ones. They work in direction and this identifies our mental existence. Mind is made every day, every minute and every second. Every second, the mind changes and we gain new experiences daily. Hence we constantly struggle and confuse while taking a decision, if the habits stored in our mind are not strong.

The mind evolves through all our positive and negative thoughts and experiences. It changes from time to time with all-new views, new knowledge gained and experiences faced. The mind of a child is completely different than that of a grown civilized human being. According to the NLP model, we face over 2+ million bits of data every second. Hence concentrating our mind on one thought is very difficult. It continuously seeks more and more, stores information, organize information, experiencing the emotions, it also regulates the body, regulates breathing, eating, and sleeping.

A human mind is a mercury, and a mercury flows in all direction and always unstable.

The Mind with Body

Mind is the delicate existence of the body. This physical body is made by the mind for its pleasure; the energy is invested for gaining experience of this world through sense organs. The change in our thought creates the energy in the nerve cells of the brain and is transferred to the physical body. This activity creates electrical and chemical changes in the body. Hence the mind is always connected to the body. The mind has a great influence over the body and the body influences the mind in return.

A healthy strengthened mind creates a healthy body. Negativity in the mind disturbs the body. If the body is sick then the mind also becomes sick. When the mind is disturbed, then the body is also disturbed. When the body and mind are disturbed then there is a change in electrical and chemical composition flow in the wrong direction. The food is not digested properly resulting in health upset. Therefore, we need to be careful in choosing our thoughts and in our thought processes. Thoughts and desires depend on the nature of the experiences we face in our daily routine and hence engaging in good desires and thought always helps us to do good deeds. For better regulation of the human system, the mind has to be in a calm state. Hence always promote noble, loving, and kind thoughts. By this, we would have harmony, health, and beauty.

The Mind with Food

Mind is the by-product of the food we consume. The Indian philosophers believed that the mind is formed by food. In Bhagavad-Gita food has been classified into three types – sattvic food, rajasic food, and Tamasic food.

As per Rebekah Miller, Food not only nourishes the body, it feeds the mind. Glucose from the food we eat acts as energy to keep the mind active and engaged. Healthy microbes present in the gut improve our cognition and emotions. Microbes in GI improves food absorption and more importantly activate neural pathway between the gut and Mind

Food has a direct link to our body and mind and play an important role in creating the mind. We experience this in our everyday schedule. Controlling the mind after heavy and junky food is very difficult.

Environment plays an important role in food intake, disorganized homes, cluttered office spaces, more distractions, and chaotic environments lead people to eat more than they would be in a controlled environment.

Caution: Let the change in food be gradual.

Role of mind during Fear

Fear is one of the common psychological diseases affecting human beings. Fear has different forms, fear of disease, fear of death, fear of losing money, etc. Fear makes people tired, sad and unsuccessful and in Covid-19, fear has increased in India and all over the world. There are many studies observed where the fear of Covid-19 is associated more with fear and anxiety, also cases of suicide have increased due to fear of Covid-19. Fear differs in people, fewer people face fear bravely, fewer are afraid of society, fewer can face an elephant but they are afraid of heights.

Causes of fear

Imagination flowing in the mind sometimes intensifies fear. Constant thinking about the future makes one fear. Fear of doing wrong things, if done thinking about the repenting. The fear in one's life makes one fear and also the courage in one's life makes one courageous. Hence, it is the mind that has manifested the experiences and gives back when the same experience is triggered.

A calm mind means courage. Developing a positive attitude, practicing positive affirmations and courage decreases anxiety and fear.

Reduce fear and anxiety though the method of Imagination and Substitution

Imagination

The mind can never be free, if one fear is over, other manifest immediately. The mind always diverts our thoughts while concentrating. Even a perfect, healthy man has some magic of imagination in mind. Most of our stored energy is wasted on unreal thoughts.

Let's say, when the mind is fully occupied with playing a game, the person does not feel any sorrow neither happiness. He is not aware of past thoughts. He is filled with so much enthusiasm and energy that he is not conscious of his body. When all such excitement is over and when his mind is free, and he gets conscious of all the sorrow and past thoughts. The power of imagination always magnifies.

Always imagine positive and pleasant thoughts.

Method of substitution

In this method, when there is a fearful thought, we need to substitute it from the thought of courage. The negative thoughts will kill themselves. Whenever depressed, we need to fill the

mind with happiness. When sick, we need fill the mind with the thoughts full of health, strength, power. Constant practice of substitution gradually gives back the hidden happiness.

If we focus our conscious thoughts to negative then sub-conscious will sincerely deliver feelings, emotions, and memories associated with that thinking type. And these feelings become our originality; this will be caught up in a rat race of negativity, fear, and anxiety.

Fear is present in attraction. When we always attach to the body, fear of death comes in. When we have a material attraction, there is a fear of losing, as material gain is for enjoyment.

Worriedness and thoughts of fear are dreadful elements within us. They kill our mind and destroy harmony, while the opposite thoughts like cheerfulness, joy, courage, love immensely improve the mental power.

Always be courageous and keep smiling.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Mind

In this conceptual model of the mind, the extreme outer layer is individualistic. The extreme outer layer as shown above are Environment, experiences, Society, food, water, and security and these are all individualistic. We all have our likes and dislikes according to the environments we live in, with the people and society, with the experiences we face in our regular day-to-day activities, the food we eat, the water we drink, and also in terms of security.

All the external factors, likes, and dislikes are stored in our memory through the 5 sense organs and these sense organs play a major role in controlling our mind. Hence, the memory so-called the storage house is an important factor in determining ourselves. The information available in the memory influences the mind and thereby acting outwards again through our body with the help of sense organs. Every day we cultivate novel thoughts, novel ideas, novel desires, and novel feelings all these are deposited into the memory of the ocean and are strongly held by the mind. New information gathers are stronger than the old ones. Both old and new information stored in memory work in symphony and this identifies our mental existence.

Hence, let us all ensure that we feed the mind with good positive experiences, a happy environment, nutritious food, a good amount of water, creating good relationships, and selfless service to others.

Overcome fear and anxiety by controlling the mind

- Renunciation of desires through sense organs

Example: A desire arises to eat Ice-cream. We should not allow the body to move to the shop to buying the Ice-cream. We should not allow the tongue to eat the Ice-cream. We should not allow the eyes to see the Ice-cream also. We should not allow our mind to concern about Ice-cream

We must outbreak the craving, from within ourself, and then alone we can control the mind perfectly with quite an ease.

- Renunciation of objects.

We are always spending our energies on Objects, the mind always likes and dwells upon the objects constantly, thinks about them very often, which must be given up then alone we can achieve true harmony, will-power and control over the mind.

Suppose you like to drink coffee every morning, ignore it for few days. After some months, the craving will slowly vanish.

- Practice happiness

The mind is loving, happy, and always in bliss. We should always check this nature within. The craving for happiness and ease is stored in the lake of the mind. We should try not to spend an excess of our energy in fulfilling our desires.

Take everything as it comes, instead of arguing and complaining. By this, we improve our mental strength and removes irritability and we will develop the power of endurance and patience

- **Fighting Failures**

Let not our failures discourage us, we will do our best. Let us not always think about our faults and failures. Let us look at them to learn from failures and then, try again. So doing, we will gain strength. The imagining part of the mind should always work along with the mind. While focus on one thing, our thoughts should not wander on another. While you are eating, think of food only. Do not think of a football match. While we play football, do not think family. The frequent cause of failure is to think of more than one thought at a time.

- **Religious practices**

If we do not give time to the inward life, we cannot enjoy worldly achievements. They may have everything money, home, family and so many more but because of fear, anxiety, and agitation, happiness is impossible. Prayer, meditation, inspection, and other such practices are necessary for life in the world.

- **Prayer**

We must be spending a daily stipulated time in prayer

Some people pray mechanically, and their minds are always away and not within God. Mechanically repeated is good initially but does not become much effective in longer run.

The first type is used by the majority of people in fulfilling the material gains. This is considered the lowest form of prayer by spiritually developed personalities.

The second type is practiced for the attainment of inner personality. For example, pray for knowledge, and love; they do not give attention to position, and others

The third kind is meditation. Here the thought is filled with God alone. And people of such devotion will not suffer from physical want.

- **Service to others**

Indian soil has been sanctified by individual souls sacrificing everything in the service of the needy. Many religious monks infused the spirit of service to their fellow monks and disciples.

The great duty for all of us is to earn a living in a dharmic way and always indulge in service of poor.

We should learn the art of working and living together. To have a better society, there must have ethical principles.

Daily routine as recommended by Sri Swami Sivananda in the book “MIND, ITS MYSTERIES AND CONTROL”

Below is the daily spiritual routine. Those who work in offices can adjust and make necessary alterations according to their convenience and time

MEDITATION	8 hours
STUDY	4 hours
WRITING	2 hours
SERVICE	2 hours
FOOD, BATH, EXERCISE	2 hours
SLEEP	6 hours

CONCLUSION

The mind requires love, and joy. Moral strength and courage is vital to face misrepresentations and misunderstanding

I hereby conclude that the mind can be controlled by understanding the conceptual model of the mind. Understanding our body-mind function and observing our thought processes leads to spiritual growth, and with spiritual growth, we can experience happiness.

The mind can be controlled by maintaining a better physique/body, control in food habits; control the sense organs by adapting to a positive environment, positive thoughts, and by our daily habits including selfless service to mankind and meditation

Also, I conclude that by controlling the mind through Imagination and substitution method, we can overcome fear and anxiety

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